
Variations and Dynamics of The Korean Speech Styles: Case of tourism workers in Bali Indonesia

I Made Suamba¹, Made Budiarsa², I Made Suastra³, Ni Made Dhanawaty⁴

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Abstract

Research on the variety of Korean spoken language that has been carried out so far generally examines the use of Korean by native speakers, while this research focuses on the use of Korean by foreigners, in this case the tourism workers in Bali. Therefore, it is very interesting to see the phenomenon of variations in the use of Korean. This study aims to find out more about the variety of speech styles used by tourism workers in Bali and the dynamics of their use in the sub-domain of tourism, such as in markets, in coffee factories, in restaurants, in watersports, in hotels, in massage/spa venues, and tours and travel. Data is in the form of recorded speeches from tourism workers when interacting with Korean tourists. The results of this study found four variations of the Korean speech styles used by tourism workers in Bali, namely the formal style, the polite style, the intimate style and the plain style. Additionally, it was found that there were dynamics in the use of the Korean language by tourism workers who had a longer duration of interaction. Apart from that, there was also a shift in the use of types of speech, namely a transition from a variety of formal speech style to the polite one, a transition from a variety of polite style to a variety of intimate style, and a mixture of types of speech style.

¹ IKIP Saraswati, Denpasar, Indonesia. Email: suamba76@yahoo.com

² Professor of Linguistics, Udayana University, Denpasar, Indonesia

³ Professor of Linguistics, Udayana University, Denpasar, Indonesia

⁴ Associate Professor of Linguistics, Udayana University, Denpasar, Indonesia

1. Introduction

As an international language, English is widely spoken in the world of tourism. The use of English is seen in almost every interaction between tourism workers and tourists (Suamba et al., 2020). English plays a vital role in the world of tourism, especially in communicating, negotiating and making transactions with tourists (Salim et al., 2012, Lu et al., 2021). Unfortunately, not all tourists who come to Bali understand English well, so proficiency in a supporting foreign language is required. One of the foreign languages that has recently become quite popular in Bali is Korean. Tourism workers in Bali have different levels of the Korean language proficiency which are influenced by the domain of work, the duration of interaction, the place where the Korean language is acquired. These differences can lead to variations in the Korean language (Ku, 2014).

Research on variations of variety in Korean initially focused on the influence of static factors such as politeness, formality, and factor deference on the choice of Korean language variants (Song, 2006). Furthermore, Strauss and Eun (2005) examined the choice of respectful speech levels in Korean. Chang (2014) examined variations in Korean speech levels and their alternations which are influenced by the inherent variable interlocutors and context of situation (age, occupation, gender and origin) (Byon, 2007; Brown & Yeon, 2019). Park (2014) examines the types and variations of the variety of Korean used by teachers and students in the classroom. The choice of language variety is dynamic and complex because it is influenced by changes in feelings, affirmation of identity and the stand of the speaker (Zuraida et al., 2020).

The research studies mentioned above generally examine the use of speech levels by native Korean speakers. Meanwhile, the use of the Korean language speech level option for non-native speakers is still rare. While the development of Korean language learning is prolific, there are still few tourism workers who are able to communicate in Korean well, it is hoped that this research is useful. The purpose of this study is to find the types of variations of Korean speech styles used by tourism workers in Bali and the dynamics of their use.

2. Materials and Methods

The sample of this research consisted of 14 tourism workers who were divided into two groups, namely tourism workers who interacted in a short period of time and tourism workers who interacted over a longer time. The first group consists of hotel employees, restaurant employees, gift shop employees, massage employees and traders in the art market. Meanwhile, the second group consisted of Korean-speaking tour guides. Data in the form of Korean language utterances from tourism actors were collected using the observation method with the recording technique.

The data for the first group were collected by direct recording of the interactions between tourists and Korean tourists in Bali. The second data set was collected with the help of a tourism driver who recorded the tour guide's speech when handling Korean guests. The collected data sets were then listened to repeatedly and transcribed into Latin letters, then translated into English. The data is then reduced and coded. Lastly, the data was grouped based on the types of Korean speech styles and analyzed based on the theory of language variation (Holmes & Wilson, 2017) and the theory of the variety of Korean speech style (Lee & Hee, 2016; Lee & Ramsey, 2001). These two theories are used to critically find and analyze variations in the Korean language used by tourism workers in Bali and the dynamics of its use.

3. Results and Discussions

Researchers classified the findings into two parts, namely the types of speech styles used by tourism workers and the dynamics of their use. This will be explained in more detail as follows.

Variety of Korean Speech Styles

Based on the data analysis, four types of variations in the level of Korean spoken by tourism workers in Bali were found as presented following.

1. The Formal Style/Differential Style (-pnita/supnita)

The use of the formal/differential style is used in the following sub-domains of tourism:

Data 1: (coffee factory)

"Ike khephi sihem cenpu ta alapikha yeca khephi ipnita. aisu ahephi ttukewun khephi kathun khephi ipnita "

'This is coffee testing. This tastes all female arabica coffee. Iced coffee or hot coffee is all the same'

Interpretation: A tourism worker, namely a coffee factory employee, explains to Korean tourists about the types of coffee in the coffee factory. She uses the formal speech style, which is characterized by the use of the sentence ending *-pnita/supnita* as in *ipnita* 'to be'. The choice of the type of speech style is related to age, social status and social distance. The coffee factory employee is younger and has an inferior status. The social distance between the coffee factory employee and the visiting tourist is not close because they have just met and interacted. These factors influence her to use the formal style.

Data 2: (hotel front office)

"Kulemyen, yeki ricothe tayhayse selmyeng tulikeyssupnita. Cikum yeki-nun lopi ipnita. yeki siktang-un twukay issupnita. Bamboo lang Jumana. Bamboo-nun yeki-ey issupnita. Yeki asia umsik issko, achim cemsim cenyek ta yekieyse tusilswu issupnita. Cosik-un sangphwum wihayse cosik sikan-un yeset sipan pwuthe yel pan kkaci. kuliko, Jumana siktang-un yeki-ey issupnita. Yeki-nun phulangsu umsik-un issko, cenyek man tusilswu issupnita "

'So, I will explain about the resort here. Now the lobby is here. There are two restaurants here. Bamboo and Jumana. Bamboo restaurant is here. There is Asian food here and you can have breakfast, lunch and dinner here. Breakfast is included, from 6.30 to 10.30. then, Jumana is here. Here French cuisine is available and only provides dinner'.

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, namely a hotel receptionist, uses a formal style speech style when explaining hotel facilities to Korean tourists who have just checked out. The use of the formal speech style is characterized by the use of the sentence ending *-ipnita / supnita* as in *selmyeng tulikeyssupnita* 'to explain', *ipnita* 'to be', *Issupnita* 'to have', and *tusilswu issupnita* 'to be able to drop in'. The choice of this type of speech style is related to social status and social distance, namely the inferior position as a service provider to tourists and the distance is not close because they have just met and started interactions.

Data 3. (Spa house)

"Kulemyen, ike hanpen posiko, cey-ka kantanhakey selmyenghaytulikeyssupnita. onul yeyyak-un aloma supa yeyyo. Pang-ulo twupwun kkaci tulekasyese ilyong sokos-ul kalaipusintaumey hansikan isipwun tongan aloma oil masaci haytuliko, nameci sikan-un supa ipnita. Supa-nun kaccilceyke haytuliko, phayk haytulikoyo. Yokco Tulekasstaka syawesinun toypnita."

'So, look at this, I'll explain it simply. You enter the room together and after changing clothes with disposable underwear, you are given aroma oil massage. The rest of the time is Spa. You will be given a scrub, skin rejuvenation for Spa treatment. After soaking in the bath tub, you can take a shower.

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, namely a spa employee, uses a formal speech style when interacting with Korean tourists. This is indicated by the use of the formal speech style sentence ending -*ipnita/supnita*, as in *selmyenghaytulikeyssupnita* 'to explain', *ipnita* 'tobe', and *toyfnita* 'you may'. The choice of the type of speech style is related to age, social status, and social distance. The Spa employee is younger and inferior than the guests. The social distance between them is not close enough because they have just met and started interactions. These are the things that encourage her to use a formal style.

Data 4 (tourist guide)

"Ney, tasi hanpen annyenghasipnikka. Palli osinkes-ul hwanyenghapnita. Hey, ney .. Yeki Issnun, help me, we are now Ipnita. Hankwukmal kaitu toyciman, hankwukmal-i mocaranikka, ihayhay cwusiko, bwuthak tulipnita. ceuy-nun ilum-i hyenci ilum wayan sualutana ipnita "

'Yes, how are you?, welcome to Bali. I am a tour guide during your stay here. Even though I am a Korean guide, because my Korean language is still lacking, please understand and help me. My local name is Wayan Suardana.'

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, namely a tourist guide, uses a formal speech style when interacting with Korean tourists. This is characterized by the use of formal sentence ending *-pnita/-supnita* such as in *hwanyenghapnita* 'to welcome', *ipnita* 'tobe', and *pwuthak tulipnita* 'to ask a favor'. The choice of the type of speech style is influenced by the context of the situation, age and social status. The context of the speech situation is that the tour guide interacts with the guests for the first time. He is younger and has an inferior status in front of the guests because he is a service provider. These are the things that influence him using the formal speech style.

2. The Polite Style (-yo)

Data 1: (coffee factory)

"Manyakey sasimyen yeki bota-nun khephi-nun senthaykhalswu isseyo. Ike wentwu kalase mek-nunkeyo. Kutaumey wancen kalwu kunyang mwul-ey tase mek-nunkeyo "

'Later, if you buy you can choose coffee here. This is coffee beans, you can have it after grinding. Then, it is coffee powder, it can be drunk by stirring in water '

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, namely a coffee employee, uses a polite style when interacting with Korean tourists. This is indicated by the use of the polite style sentence ending (-yo) as in *senthaykhalswu isseyo* 'able to choose', and *mek-nunkeyo* 'to eat'. The choice of the type of polite style is influenced by factors of age, social status and social distance. The coffee employee is younger and has an inferior status, but the social distance between her and the guests starts to get closer after interacting for a while.

Data 2: (water sport)

"Mwul sok-ey tulekamyen mal-i mochanikka, ilehkey kwaynchanhayo"

'If you go into the water, you can not speak, it's fine like this'

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, namely marine tourism instructors, uses a polite style when interacting with the guests. This is indicated by the use of the polite style sentence ending -yo as in *kwaynchanhayo* 'no problem'. the instructor is older than the guests (honeymooner couple), but has a lower social status. Meanwhile, the social distance is not so close because the interaction is just starting. This is what encourages him to use a polite style.

Data 3: (hotel front office)

"Yeki-nun meyin swuyengcang-ey Isseyo. swuyengcang yeph-ey phwul ba isseyo. phwul an-ey kantanha-key umsik ina umlyu tusilswu issupnita. yeki kyenglak supa to issupnita. phaykhici ilase phoham-i issnunkeyeyyo. Nayil molay cosik-un pilla-eyse phullothing-ulo ahop si pan-ey. cenyek siksanun Bamboo siktang-eyse ilkop si-ey sicakhapnita. macimak-ulo yeki-eyse wenswungi manhi issese ancen yuli mwun-ul cal tatacwuseyyo. manyakey wenswungi issumyen palo yeng pen-ulo cenhwahaseyyo "

'Here is the main swimming pool. There is a pool bar beside the pool. In the swimming pool you can eat and drink simple dishes. There is also a sport massage. This is included because of the package. Tomorrow, you have floating breakfast at the villa at 9 o'clock, dinner at the bamboo restaurant starting at 7. Finally, because there are lots of monkeys here, close the safety glass door. If there is a monkey later, call number zero '

Interpretation:

A Tourism worker, namely a hotel receptionist, uses a polite style when interacting with Korean guest. This is marked by the use of a polite style sentence ending -yo as in *isseyo* 'to have', *issnunkeyeyyo* 'probably have', and *cenhwahaseyyo* 'to make a phone call'. The choice of this speech style is influenced by social status and social distance factors. The status of the hotel receptionist is inferior to the guests, but because they have interacted for a while, the social distance between them is reduced. This is the factors that influences her to use the polite style.

Data 4. (Thai massage house)

"Masaci patko, hankwukmal-lo twayo. ettehsupnikka? aphu epseyo?. ney, kunyang sokos man ipko kawun kalaipusiko, pay kasum masaci epseyo. oil to anpaluseyyo "

'When you get a massage you may speak in Korean, What do you think? nobody hurts? Yes, just wear underwear, change your clothes with massage clothes and no belly and chest massage. Oil is also not applied.'

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, namely a massage parlor employee, uses a polite style when interacting with Korean tourists. This is indicated by the use of the polite style sentence ending -yo as in *twayo* 'you may', *epseyo* 'have no' and *anpaluseyyo* 'not to apply'. The choice of this polite style is influenced by factors of age, social status and social distance between the employee and the guests. He is younger and has inferior status. The informal background of the speech encourages the employee to choose the polite style rather than the formal one.

Data 5. (Spa house)

"Supa-nun kakcilceyke haytuliko, phayk haytulikoyo. yokco tulekasstaka syawesinun toypnita, discuss tongan. kutaumey yokco-nun paniyong intey senthayk hasinuntwayyo. manyakey antulekakosiphumyen, taysiney masaci kilkey patulswu isseyo. "

'For the spa treatment, we will serve you a scrub and skin rejuvenation. After soaking in the bath tub, you can take a shower during that time. then, it is a shared bathtub so you can choose. Later if you don't want to bathe, you can get a longer massage for the remaining time '

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, namely a spa employee, use a polite style when interacting with the Korean guests. This is indicated by the use of the polite style sentence ending -yo as in *haytulikoyo* 'to give', *senthayk hasinuntwayyo* 'you may choose' and *patulswu Isseyo* ' you may receive' The use of this style is influenced by factors of age, social status and social distance. The spa officer is young and has an inferior status, but the social distance between them is closer because they have been interacting for a while.

Data 6: (Tourist guide)

"Othopai thamyen com heylmeys isseyahapnita. ankulemyen kyengchal capayo. ku kyengchal pota sako nalttay cincca wihemhayyo. catongcha-to kathi issunikka wihemhayyo "

'If you ride a motorcycle you have to have a helmet, otherwise you will be arrested by the police. If there is an accident it is really dangerous compared to being caught by the police. Riding motorbike beside the cars is dangerous.

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, namely a tourist guide, uses a polite style when interacting with his guests. This is indicated by the use of the sentence ending polite style - yo as in *capayo* 'to catch', and *wihemhayyo* ' to be dangerous'. The use of this speech style is influenced by factors of age, social status and social distance. The tourist guide is younger and has a lower status, but the social distance between them is rather close, and in an informal situation, so he prefers using a polite style.

3. The Intimate Style (-a/-a)

Data 1. (Ubud market)

Trader: *'Thank you ladies. This one phalman rupiah, that one kwuman lwuphi, ney tasoskay. elma ssaakey siptalla.*

'Thank you ladies. This one is phalman rupiah. That one 90 thousand Rupiah, yes five pieces. How cheap is 10 dollars'

Guest: *'Ike discoun antwayyo?*

This can't be discounted? '

Trader: *'elma? how many? hankay twukay? phalman twukay phalman lwuphia '.*

'How much, how many? one or two? Two pieces eighty thousand rupiah, 80 thousand rupiah '

Traders: *'ney, twukay, yelkay'.*

'Ye, two, ten

Guest: *'ywuk man lwuphia'*

'60 thousand Rupiah '

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, namely a trader in the Ubud market, use the intimate style when interacting with the Korean customers. This is indicated by the use of the intimate style sentence ending as in *elma* 'how much' and the omission of the copula *ita* 'to be' as in the *hankay twukay?* 'one or two?' *elma ssaakey siptalla* 'the cheap price is ten dollars.' The use of the intimate style is influenced by Korean language proficiency, cultural understanding and the place where the Korean language is acquired. The trader is self-taught in Korean, so she does not know the Korean language fluently, nor the socio-cultural context behind a speech.

Data 2. (coffee factory)

yeki kongcang-ey sahyang koyangi-nun yasayng sahyang koyangi. Ike-nun hana-ey payk kulaym-ey. payk archive talle. i ceyil pissan khephi. original Ike.

'Here the mongoose in the factory are wild civets. 100 grams per one, the price is 150 dollars. This is the most expensive coffee. This is original.'

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, namely a coffee factory employee, uses the intimate style when explaining about civet coffee to the Korean customers. This is shown by the omission of the copula *ita* 'tobe' at the end of nominal sentences such as *yasayng sahyang koyangi* 'wild chivet', *payk osip talle* 'one hundred fifty dollars', *i ceyil pissan khephi* 'this the most expensive coffee', original *Ike* 'this original'. The use of intimate style is influenced by the factor of Korean language proficiency, understanding of Korean customs and culture, and the influence of her mother tongue on the acquisition of Korean language.

Data 3. (water sport)

mwul sok-ey tulekamyen kwaynchanh kho-lo swumsi swumsi ilenke kwaynchanha. chenchenhi. mwul sok-ey tulekamyen swuyeng mocthay ilehkey kwaynchanha. mwul sok-ey tulekamyen wekhe swuyeng antway. mwul sok-ey tulekamyen il mithe sam mithe mata kwi aphayo. ip-ulo man. mwul sok-ey tulekamyen kathi insuthanta mwul-ey kapayo. Insuttanta kathi tulekamyen chenchenhi.

'If you go into the water it's okay to breathe by mouth.. to breathe like this is fine but slowly. If you get into the water and can't swim, this is fine. If you go into the water you are not allowed to swim while you are walking. If you get into the water your ear will hurt every one to three meters, breathe only with your mouth. If you go into the water, the assistant will go to the water too. If the assistant get into the water together, just slow down'

Interpretation:

The tourism worker, namely a sea walker instructor, uses the intimate style when explaining the sea walker procedure to the Korean customers. It is marked by the omission of the polite style sentence ending *-yo* at the end of verbs such as in *ilenke kwaynchanha* 'it's okay like this', *swuyeng mocthay ilehkey kwaynchanha* 'if you can't swim it's fine like this'. The use of intimate style is influenced by the factor of Korean language proficiency and understanding of Korean customs and culture.

Data 4. (hotel front office)

Hotelier: *aney, hanpen*
 'No, only once'
 Guest: *hanpen man iciyo? hanpen man*
 'Just once right? just once'
 Guest: *molay molay*
 'next time'
 Guest: *molay ahopsi pan-ulo halkkeyyo.*
 'I'll do it tomorrow at 9'
 Hotelier: *molay ahopsi pan*
 'Tomorrow at 9'

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, a hotel front office staff, uses an intimate style when explaining about floating breakfast to the Korean guests which is marked by (1) the use of in-formal lexicons such as *aney* 'no' instead of *aniyo*. (2) omitting the use of the copula *ita* 'tobe' at the end of nominal sentences as in *hanpen, molay ahopsi pan* 'once, tomorrow at half past nine'. In this case, the use of intimate style is influenced by the perception of the worker to becoming closer to the guests.'

Data 5. (restaurant)

guest: *selthang akka nehko kwayncha*
 "It was okay with sugar"
 waitress: *kwaynchana?*
 'It is okay?'
 guest: *yo yo*
 'Add the suffix yo'
 guest: *selthang akka nehko kwayncana*
 'It was okay with sugar'
 waitress: *ah alase*
 'Ah ... got it'
 guest: *kwaynchana no, kwaynchanayo.*
 'You can't use *kwaynchana*, use *kwaynchanayo*'

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, a waitress, uses an intimate style when interacting with Korean guests ordering drinks. The use of the intimate style is characterized by the omission of the polite style sentence ending -yo at the end of verbs as in *kwanchana* 'it's okay', and *alase* 'I got it'. The context of the speech situation is that the waitress is much younger and has a more inferior position because she provides services to the guests and the social distance is not so close because it is the first time they have met. Based on the context of the situation above, the use of the intimate style is inaccurate, causing the guests inconvenience as shown in the speech of *kwaynchana..no, kwaynchanyo* "You can't use *kwaynchana*, use *kwaynchanayo*". The use of the intimate style here is influenced by the Korean language proficiency and understanding of Korean culture which is still lacking. This is caused by the place where the Korean language is acquired, namely self-taught.

Data 6. (tourist guide)

Guide: *ike ?, ah ike olay olay hanunke isstaka iyaki haseyyo.*

'This?' Ah..this long. long massage. please talk later. '

Guest: *yey*

Guide: *eti-ka hako sipheyo?*

'Where do you want it'

Guest: *ek kay*

'shoulder'

Guide: *ike hako kutaume? Helicopters Ike-nun?*

'This then: this waist, waist?

Guide: *anunke isseyo? ama swuswul hanunke? Swuswul hanunke cenhye epseyo?*

'There is no massage?' Maybe the part that was operated on? there was no operation at all? '

Guest: *elkwul, elkwul anhallayyo.*

'face. I don't want a face massage '

Guide: *ah ... kulay, pal?*

'Oh, I see. feet?

Guests: *pal, kwayncanhayo. Ekkay-lang, yeki-lang.*

'Feet it's okay. waist and here. '

Interpretation:

A tourism worker, a tourist guide, uses an intimate style when asking the Korean guests before getting spa services. The use of the intimate style is characterized by the omission of the polite style sentence ending -yo as in *kulay* instead of *kulayyo* (2) removing the copula *ita* 'to be' at the end of nominal sentences as in *ike* 'this', *ikenun heli heli, pal* 'this waist, waist, leg'. This is influenced by several factors including: the guide is older than the honeymooner; has closer social distance because he has handled them for several days; and the context of informal speech situations so he uses an intimate style.

4. The Plain Style (-ta)

Data 1 (water sport)

Instructors: mwul sok-ey tulekamyen mal-i mochanikka, ilehkey kwaynchanhayo (gesture: finger movements form an okay sign). Ilehkey nakasey (gesture: finger movement), wi-lo ka (gesture: movement of the thumb facing up), mwuncey issta (gesture: shake the palm of the hand).

'Because we can't speak when we get into the water, like this means okay. like this it means going out (thumb pointing up). there is a problem (palm shake shake)

Traveler: mwuncey issta

'There is a problem'

Interpretation:

The use of plain style in the speech data above is indicated by the use of the lexicon *issta* 'to have' as in *mwuncey issta* 'there is problem'. This usage is influenced by some factors, such as the Korean language proficiency and culture which is still lacking because the worker is self-taught in the language.

Data 2 (restaurant)

guest: *meknun to manhney*.

'Food a lot lo'

Waitress: *Kuke Talk Aniya*

'It's not a chicken'

guest: *talk aniya?*

'Not chicken?'

Waitress: *ney, ike-nun papeykhyu*.

'Yes, it's barbecue'

Interpretation:

The use of plain style in the speech data above is indicated by the use of the sentence ending *-ya* as in *kuke talk aniya* 'that's not chicken'. The use of plain style is inappropriate because the waiter has inferior status to the guests. Additionally, she is much younger than the guests. This is influenced by her lack of understanding of Korean language and culture. The waiter is self-taught in the Korean language, and does not understand the use of the Korean speech styles appropriately.

Data 3. (tourist guide)

Guide: *othopai-to keuy epscanayo, kelese kaya toynuntey, salamtul-un kenkanghayyo. Kenkangey coha*.

'In the past, there were not any motorbikes, so we had to walk. the people are healthy. their health is good.

Guest: *kenkangey cohta*

'Good health'

Guide: *kenkangey cohta*.

'Good health'

Interpretation:

A tourist guide uses a plain style when explaining the transportation system in Bali. The use of plain style here is characterized by the use of verbs with the plain style sentence ending *-ta* as in

kenkangey cohta 'good health'. The choice of this variety is influenced by the informal conversation situation, the factor of the age of the tourist guide - who is older than his customers, and the desire to make the social distance closer so that he follows the speech style used by the guests.

The Dynamics of the Use of Various Korean Speech Styles

The choice of speech style carried out by the tourism workers can change according to the context of the situation that occurs. This is generally seen in the utterances of the tourism workers which have a longer duration of interactions. At the beginning of the interaction, they generally choose a form of formal speech style or the polite style. However, after interacting with the guests for a longer period of time, there is a tendency for them to switch to a more familiar type of speech style or to have a mixed variety of speeches. This will be explained in more detail in the following data.

Data 1 (tourist guide 1/day 1)

Guide: *ney, tasi hanpen annyenghasipnikka. Palli osinkes-ul hwanyenghapnita. Hey, ney .. Yeki Issnun, help me, we are now Ipnita. Hankwukmal kaitu toyciman, hankwukmal-i mocaranikka, ihayhay cwusiko, bwuthak tulipnita.*

'Yes, once again good evening. welcome to Bali. yes, yes. I am your guide as long as you are in Bali. Even though I am a Korean speaking tour guide, my Korean language is still lacking, please understand and ask for your help '

Guide: *ceuy-nun ilum-i hyenci ilum wayan sualutana ipnita. Ney, com antoypnita himtulnikka. Kutaumey hankwuk ilum ilpwu-lo mantulko issupnita. Hankwuk ilum-i cang tay min ipnita.*

'My name is wayan Suartana, yes, because it was quite difficult to say, so I made up a Korean name. my Korean name is cang tay min '

Interpretation:

The speech data above shows the dynamics of the use of the variety of Korean speech style. At the beginning of the speech, he chooses a formal style which is marked by the use of the formal style sentence ending *-pnita* in positive sentences and sentence ending *-pnikka* in interrogative one. The use of this type of speech style is related to the status of the guests and social distance. After interacting for 2 days, the guide gradually began to switch to using a variety of polite style to reduce the level of formality as shown in the following data.

Data (day 2)

Guide: *khomoto-nun wuli intoneysia-nun khomoto sem kkaci issupnita. kutaumey ta tomabaym-un ama intoneysia-eyse cakun to eyse pwuthe ceyil khun kkaci ta intoneysia eyso issupnita. nacwungey palli issumyen, kukes-un mwusepci anhayo.*

'Komodo in Indonesia to the island of Komodo. Then all the lizards, from the biggest to the smallest one are in Indonesia. Later if there are lizards in Bali it's not scary.

Guide: *wenlay silhehayyo?*

'Really scared?'

Guest: *anio, emma*

'No, mother'

Guide: *a kulayyo, wenlay epseyo, pang-ey epseyo. Nayil-un wenswungi issupnita, wenswungi.*

I see, there really isn't. tomorrow there are monkeys, monkeys'

Guest: *yey*

'yes'

Guide: wenswungi cohayo?

'Like monkeys'

Guest: taykay cohayo

'really like'

Guide: *kuliko, wenswungi issciman, mancimyen antwayyo. Com yasayng wenswungi inikka, mwuleyo*

then, even if there are monkeys, it should not be touched, because the monkeys are a quite wild, they'll bite '

Interpretation:

The speech data above is the speech data of the tourist guide and Korean customers interactions on the second day. This data shows a shift in the use of speech style from formal style to polite style. At the beginning, they started with a formal style which was marked by the use of the formal style sentence ending *-pnita/-supnita* such as in *wuli intoneysia-nun khomoto sem kkaci issupnita* 'we have even Komodo island' and *ceyil khun kkaci ta intoneysia eyso issupnita* '. then he slowly switched to using the polite style (*-yo*) as in *kukes-un mwusepci anhayo* 'that is not scary', *wenley silhehayyo* 'dislike', *pang-ey epseyo* 'no monkey in the room'. So this diversion shift was carried out by the guide to reduce the formality and distance.

Data 2 (tourist guide 2/day 1)

Guide: *yey, talun teyyo kayo. Ike wenlay syophing-un macimak kaseyyo. Ike macimak hamyen sankwan epseyo. Wenlay macimak-ey wuli sinlang hako sinpwunim-i sikan-i wancen manhayo.*

'Yes, go somewhere else. it's actually we go shopping on the last day. this can be done on the last day. actually our bride and bridegroom have so much time on the last day '

Guest: *macimaknal yo?*

'On the last day?'

Guide: *yey, pihayngki hansu icanayo hansu samsipwun ieyyo.*

'Yes, the flight is 1 o'clock, 1.30 am'

Guest: *macimaknal-ey halswu issnun sikan-i isseyo?*

'Is there time for the last day to do it?'

Guide: *yeki syophing sikan-i tases sikan ieyyo.*

here the shopping time is 5 hours'

Interpretation:

The data above shows that at the beginning of the interaction, the tour guide tends to use the formal style which is marked by the use of the polite style sentence ending *-yo* such as in *kaseyyo* 'to go', *epseyo* 'have no', and *ieyyo* 'tobe'. The use of polite style here shows that the tour guide as a service provider maintains a distance from the Korean customers, but after a longer interaction, he tends to switch to intimate style or use a mixed type of speech style as shown by the following data.

Data: (day 2)

Guide: *eti-ka hako sipheyo?*

'Where do you want?'

Guest: *ekkey*

'shoulder'

Guide: *ike hako kutaumey? heli heli Ike-nun?*

'This then? this is the waist waist? '

Guide: *anunke isseyo? ama swuswul hanunke? Swuswul hanunke cenhye epseyo?*

'Is there anything you don't get a massage? surgery marks? There was no surgery at all? '

Guest: *elkwul, elkwul anhallayyo.*

face, I don't want facial massage '

Guide: *ah ... kulay, pal?*

'Ah so, leg?

Guest : *pal, kwayncanhayo. Ekkay-lang, yeki-lang.*

'Legs, it's okay, shoulders and here'

Interpretation:

The speech data above shows that the tour guide has shifted the speech style from the polite style to the intimate style. At first, he used the polite style sentence ending (-yo) as in *eti-ka hako sipheyo* 'where do you want?' then switched to using the intimate style by eliminating the copula *ita* 'to be' as in *heli heli ikenun* 'waist, waist, this'. then switched back to polite style as in *anunke isseyo* 'are there any part of body you don't want to get massage', *swusul hanunke cenhye epseyo* 'no part of your body has been operated'. Subsequent speech shows a transition back to intimate speech style by the omission of the polite style sentence ending -yo in verbs such as in *kulay, pal* 'oh so leg'. Therefore, the guide changes the variety dynamically based on the mood and adjusts the speech style to that chosen by the guests.

Data 3: (tourist guide 3/day 1)

Guide: *palli-eyse osinkes-ul hwanyenghapnita. Ku palli kyeysinun tongan cey-ka cikum pwuthe macimaknal kkaci anayhaytulikeyssupnita. Akka ce ilum-i tikha, thika sacinki.*

'Welcome to Bali. I will accompany you while in Bali from now until the last day will accompany. As I told you earlier my name is Dika, digital camera.

Guest: ha ha ha

Guide: *kisa ilum-i anttala. cey sacinki, sacinki. Yeki konghang ilumi-i Ngurah Rai kwukcey konghang ipnita. Kuliko, Ngurah Rai-ka greeting ilum cangkun anun ilum. teynphasalu-nun ciek ilum. Palli swuto-nun teynphasalu. Ike sinhon yehayng chwuka tulipnita. Kyelhonsik eceyk ucekkey? three weeks, two weeks.*

'The driver's name is Antara. I am camera, camera. The airport here is called Ngurah international airport. then, Ngurah rai is the name of a person, the name of a hero. Denpasar is the name of the area, the capital of Bali. this as a congratulation for your marriage. when you get married? yesterday two days ago? 3 weeks 2 weeks

Guide: *yeki-nun 2013 nyen-ey tasi limoteylling haysstako issupnita. Ku 2014 nyen-ey cen-ey wancen ancohayo. Nemwu teleweyo.*

'Here he said it was renovated in 2013. Before 2014 it was not very good. too dirty. '

Interpretation:

The speech data above shows the shift in speech style used by a tour guide when interacting with a Korean customer upon arrival at the airport. At the beginning, formal speech style is used which is marked by the use of the formal style sentence ending -pnita as in *palli-eyse osinkes-ul hwanyenghapnita, macimaknal kkaci anayhaytulikeyssupnita*. but in the next speech he chose the

intimate style shown by the omission of copula *ita* 'to be' as in *Akka ce ilum-i tikha, thika sacinki* 'As I told you earlier my name is Dika, digital camera'. *kisa ilum-i anttala* 'driver's name is Antara'. *Cey sacinki, sacinki* 'I am camera'. Subsequently then he returned to the formal style as in *kwukcey konghang ipnita* 'it is an international airport'. Then he switches again to intimate styles such as *Ngurah Rai-ka salam ilum cangkun anun ilum* 'Ngurah Rai is a well-known person', *teynphasalunun ciek ilum* 'Denpasar is a name of area'. *Palli swuto-nun teynphasalu* 'the capital city of Bali is Denpasar'. Then he continued to formal styles such as *Ike sinhon yehayng chwuka tulipnita* 'this as a congratulation for your marriage, but in the next speech, he again switched to using the intimate style as in *kyelhonsik ecey kucekkey?* 'did you get married yesterday, two days ago?' at the beginning of the speech, the tour guide switches the speech style repeatedly between the formal and intimate style, this seemed to be done naturally, which was influenced by Korean language skills, cultural understanding and language transfer. In the next speech, the he switched to using the polite style (-yo) as a response because the guests used the polite style as shown in the following data.

Guest: *nalssi-ka cikum ilehkey teweyo?*

'The weather is like this hot right now?

Guide: *aney, cikun-un yakhan siwenhayyo. Hey, ney hangsang chilwel phalwel nalssi-ka siwenhayyo. Yeki, ku Ngurah rai kinyem tongsang. Ku nalssi nun cikun-un. Ceyil cohayo. Iwel sawel siwenhayyo, stimulate. Kuliko, ceyil tewun nalssi-ka siwel, siwel civilian ceyil teweyo. Samwel sawel sai-ey kuttay-to teweyo. Kuliko, owel ywukwel chilwel nalssi-ka ceyil siwenhayyo. Kuntey cikun yakhan palam-i manhi pwuleyo.*

'No, it's a little cool now. yes, yes July and August the weather is always cool. ah here, Ngurah Rai memorial statue. the weather is the best now. February April is always cool. then, the hottest weather is on October, October November the hottest. Between March and April it is also hot. the end of May, June, July are the coolest ones. but now the wind is blowing quite a bit. '

Interpretation:

The data above shows that the tour guide uses the polite style after the guests asks him by using a type of speech in a form of polite style such as *teweyo* 'hot'. The transition to polite style is indicated by the use of the polite style sentence ending *-yo* as in *siwenhayyo* 'cool', *cohayo* 'good', *teweyo* 'hot' and *pwuleyo* 'to blow'. So, the guide as a service provider switches the speech style from formal style and the polite one which is adjusted to the speech style used by the guests. The use of intimate style here is only found in nominal sentences that do not use verbs, in this case by omitting the copula *ita* 'to be', so it can be concluded that the use of the intimate style here is only an accidental error due to the influence of Indonesian language which does not require the presence of to be at the end of sentences like Indonesian.

Data: (tourist guide 4/ day 1)

Guide: *annyenghasipnikka?*

'How are you'

Guest: *annyenghaseyyo.*

'How are you'

Guide: *hanpen te palli sem-ey osin kes-ul hwanyenghapnita.*

'Once again welcome to Bali.'

Guide: *ney, ce-nun Ayu Krisna lako hanuntey, palli yehayngsa-ey hankwukmal annaywen imye, Krisna lako man pwulle cwusipsio. Chewum poypkeyssupnita. Mannase pankapsupnita.*

yes, my name is Ayu Krisna, a Korean speaking tour guide from Bali tour. Please just call me Krisna. nice to meet you'

Guide: *Encey Kyelhon Haysseyo?*

'When did you get married?'

Guest: *cinan cwu, thoyoil*

'Last week, Saturday.'

Guide: *kyelhonsik chwuka tulipnita. Palli-ey issnun tongan hayngpok haseyyo, ney.*

'Wishing you all the best in your new life. I wish you Happy while in Bali '

Guide: *kuliko, coysonghapnita. oppa, enni, enni oppa pwulusimyen kwayncanhsupnikka?*

"Then, I'm sorry, but can I call you as brother and sister?"

Interpretation:

The speech data above shows that the tour guide tends to use a formal speech style at the beginning of the interaction such as in *annyenghasipnikka?* 'greeting', *hwanyenghapnita* 'welcome', *pwulle cwusipsio* 'please call'. Chewum poypkeyssupnita 'meet for the first time'. Mannase pankapsupnita 'nice to meet you', *kyelhonsik chwuka tulipnita* 'congratulation on your wedding', *coysonghapnita* 'I am sorry' and *pwulusimyen kwayncanhsupnikka* 'Is it okay to call you'. She then switched to using polite style when responding to the guests' question using polite style, as shown in the following data

Guest: *khleytis khatu toyciyo?*

'Can I use a credit card, can't I?'

Guide: *khleytis khatu sayong haci maseyyo, sinay-se. Sinay-se, sinayse yeki Krisna issумыen, kwayncanhuntey epeмыen cosim haseyyo !. yocum-un Ceci me haphe yeph-ey hyenci greetings man an salayo. Yocum-un cwungkwuk salam, talun nala salamtul-i to palli-ey salanikka, kukettaymwuney somaychiki kuke cosimhaseyyo! Wenlay, wenlay-nun wihem haci ... wihem haci anhayo.*

'Don't use a credit card in town. In the city, if there is Krisna, it's okay, if Krisna is not with you, be careful. now The people that live near the hotel are not only local people but also foreigners so there might be many pickpockets, so be careful of snatching. it is actually not that dangerous. '

Interpretation:

The speech data above shows that the guide switched to using the polite style (-yo) when she realized the choice of speech style used by the guests, namely the polite style, such as *khleytis khatu toyciyo* 'credit card is accepted here, isn't it?'. the use of polite style here is characterized by the use of the polite style sentence ending -yo such as *salayo* 'to live', *haci anhayo* 'don't do that'. The use of these speech style is carried out to accommodate the choices of interlocutors's speech style to create closeness and reduce distance.

4. Conclusion

In this study, it is found that there are four types of speech style used by tourism workers in Bali when interacting with Korean tourists, namely: formal speech style; the polite style; intimate style; and the plain style. Apart from that, there was also a shift in the use of speech style, namely a shift from formal style to the polite style, from polite style to intimate style, as well as a mixture of speech style which were generally influenced by the desire of tourism workers to accommodate the customers' speech style. Besides, it is also influenced by their Korean language proficiency and cross culture understanding.

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